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Business Model Design and Evaluation Results

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Acronyms

AISBL	Association Internationale sans but Lucratif (Association without Lucrative purpose)
API	Application Programming Interface
BMC	Business Model Canvas

DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DTC	Data & Tool Committee
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
GoTriple	The Discovery Platform Developed by the TRIPLE Project
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NPO	Non-Profit Organisation
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
RI	Research Infrastructure
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SME	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprise
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
USP	Unique Selling Point
VPC	Value Proposition Canvas

Publishable Summary

Within the present report, we outline the process and progress in terms of Business Model (BM) design and Business Model evaluation. The report provides an overview of the TRIPLE Business Model development approach and a brief description of the current status of the GoTriple Platform.

Besides a summary of our Horizon Results Booster activities, we present the entire Business Model (BM) design journey, which includes a review of the used business analysis methods and insights into the crucial factors for developing a successful BM. In the field of BM “Desirability”, we illustrate our activities to match the customer requirements with the offered services of GoTriple by using the Value Proposition Canvas. In terms of BM “Viability”, we focus our activities on identifying possible revenue possibilities for GoTriple, resulting in concepts for donation and membership solutions. In the BM “Feasibility” area, we outline the TRIPLE Governance Model (GoTriple Committee), which should act as an organisational body to ensure economic sustainability for GoTriple after the project ends.

Concerning BM testing, we demonstrate the development and mapping of assumptions and the subsequent transformation into test procedures (test cards), including the definition of test methods, metrics and criteria. Hereafter we provide the outcome of a Risk Assessment of the GoTriple Platform divided into four risk factors (Partnership-, Technological-, Market-, and IPR/Legal Risk Factors).

Finally, we present the updated GoTriple Business Models divided into the two most important customer groups (Researchers, Institutions) in a short description and presented utilising the Lean Canvas.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Within the TRIPLE project, we follow the approach promoted by the European Commission (EC) that publicly-funded research should lead to the exploitation of results, which goes one step further than the mere production and dissemination of new scientific knowledge¹. With our project activities, we want to overcome the "European paradox" and show that translating scientific advances into marketable innovations is possible. Our understanding of innovation is not only promoting dissemination but especially the subsequent exploitation of the project results. Considering the increasing demand for OS resources and the growing number of OS platforms, it is relevant to strategically design an economically sustainable business model for the GoTriple platform. Since GoTriple will be one of OPERAS Research Infrastructure (RI) services², the business model considerations must be well coordinated with OPERAS.

The present report is the third outcome from work package WP7 (Innovation, Exploitation, and Sustainability), which aims at creating a valuable and viable business model for GoTriple that is sustainable beyond the project end. Within WP7 and its assigned tasks, we are continuously detailing exploitation plans and innovation and commercialisation activities. These include:

- constant monitoring of the competition
- designing business models for GoTriple and related project KER's
- testing/evaluation of business models
- refining the TRIPLE exploitation roadmap

1.1 Business Model Development

The project activities are generally guided by Alan Cooper's interaction design principle: "A successful digital product needs to be desirable, viable and feasible".³ These principles are also applied in developing a suitable platform Business Model in the project's exploitation considerations.

By Business Model, we understand a description or model representing a firm's logic to create, provide and capture value from and for its stakeholders.⁴ According to Osterwalder et al.,⁵ a

¹ European Commission (2013): How to convert Research into Commercial Success Story

<https://era.gv.at/object/document/751>

² <https://www.operas-eu.org/services/>

³ Cooper, A., Reimann, R., & Cronin, D. (2007) *About face 3: the essentials of interaction design*. John Wiley & Sons.

⁴ Bouwman, H., Vos, H. d. & Haaker, T. (2008) *Mobile service innovation and business models*. Berlin: Springer 9-30

⁵ Osterwalder, A. (2004) *The business model ontology: A proposition in a design science approach*. Dissertation. University of Lausanne. Switzerland.

business model is a "blueprint" for running a business. To structure the results in an initial BM for the GoTriple platform, we use the BM Canvas (BMC) framework from Osterwalder & Pigneur.⁶

Since GoTriple will act as a central mediator for various stakeholders (e.g. users, data repositories, research institutes, publishers, libraries), a multi-sided and multi-stakeholder BM needs to be considered. The interest in multi-sided platforms has increased with the rise of digital platforms such as Uber, Airbnb or Booking.com.⁷ They create value, acting as intermediaries by connecting users and facilitating interaction between them.⁸

Generally, a well-designed and well-tested business model is the key success factor for the sustainable exploitation of the TRIPLE project's main result, the GoTriple discovery platform. The GoTriple business model must be thought of in relation to the global business model of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). To do that, the TRIPLE project will carefully follow the work done in the EOSC governance project (answer to 5a of the H2020 call [INFRAEOSC-5 "Support to the EOSC Governance"](#)), to which the TRIPLE consortium has strong links (through the [GO FAIR Implementation Networks](#), especially [CO-OPERAS](#)). The work done in the project led by GEANT answers to the H2020 call INFRA EOSC-01 ["Access to commercial services through the EOSC hub"](#) about public procurements and access to commercial services. We consider GoTriple a specific service provided and sustained by the OPERAS Research Infrastructure (RI). Its business model will also consider this interlink.

For the early design of a BM, Bland and Osterwalder⁹ propose a model for testing business ideas. As depicted in Figure 1, the crucial factors for designing and testing a successful BM are Feasibility, Desirability, and Viability. The validation of these criteria is crucial for creating an economically sustainable business model. The BMC building blocks that need to be considered for BM feasibility are key activities, partners, and resources. To validate desirability, it is necessary to check whether the right customer segments are addressed and whether the services and products meet the customer's needs. Concerning viability, the relevant BMC building blocks are revenue streams and cost structure.

⁶ Osterwalder, Alexander & Pigneur, Yves (2010). *Business Model Generation. A Handbook for Visionaries, Game Changers, and Challengers*. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.

⁷ Hein, A., Schrieck, M., Riasanow, T., Setzke, D.S., Wiesche, M., Böhm, M. and Krcmar, H. (2020) Digital platform ecosystems, *Electronic Markets*, Vol. 30 Nos 87-98, pp. 87-98.

⁸ Sanchez-Cartas, J.M. and Leon, G. (2019) Multi-sided Platforms and Markets: A Literature Review, available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325225786>

⁹ Bland, David J. & Osterwalder, A. (2020) *Testing business ideas*. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, p. X.

FIGURE 1. COMBINATION OF COOPER ET AL. INTERACTION DESIGN PRINCIPLE¹⁰ WITH THE BMC BUILDING BLOCKS, ACCORDING TO BLAND & OSTERWALDER.¹¹

1.2 Actual Status of GoTriple Platform

At the time of writing, 4.247.599 documents (publications and datasets) are accessible via a pipeline where data are ingested, classified, enriched and categorised so that users can easily find and retrieve them. The following aggregators and data providers are progressively imported into the platform: DOAJ, EKT, Isidore (which includes DOAB and OAPEN), OpenAIRE, Biblioteka Nauki, CESSDA, ZRC-SAZU and COIMBRA. Other major aggregators, including Europeana and BASE will be integrated before the end of the project. In addition to the aggregators, the platform will also harvest data from approximately 400 repositories. Both aggregators and providers will cover the eleven languages of GoTriple (Croatian, English, French, German, Greek, Italian, Spanish, Polish, Portuguese, Ukrainian and Slovenian by the end of 2022). 27 SSH disciplines are also covered in each of the eleven languages.

GoTriple currently allows multilingual search, which means that users can find publications in a specific language by using keywords in one of the eleven languages supported by the platform. A TRIPLE thesaurus is integrated into the platform containing exactly 2565 concepts available in all languages. Documents are annotated with the concepts of the TRIPLE thesaurus on the page of each document.

¹⁰ Cooper, A., Reimann, R., & Cronin, D. (2007) *About face 3: the essentials of interaction design*. John Wiley & Sons.

¹¹ Bland, David J. & Osterwalder, A. (2020) *Testing business ideas*. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, p. X.

The search engine allows different filters such as publication type, author, year and discipline. Figure 2 (right) shows the results for “french art history” authors. The number of publications per author containing this concept is indicated in front of each author. Clicking on the number of publications per author gives access to the details of the publications.

FIGURE 2. SCREENSHOT OF MAIN PAGE AND SEARCH RESULTS

Among the six planned discovery features, the following five have already been implemented:

- Textual Search
- Visual Search (Knowledge Map, Streamgraph)
- Social Network (Trust Building System)
- Recommender
- Crowd-Funding

1.3 Objectives and Structure of the Report

The present report outlines the process and progress in terms of Business Model design and Business Model testing. The results are, on the one hand, further developments of the GoTriple BM focusing on the two main customer groups - the end-user (researcher) and SSH-focused institutions such as universities, libraries and research centres. On the other hand, the report provides BM testing results, which serve as important input for the TRIPLE Business Plan and exploitation roadmap.

The main objectives of the Report on Business Model Design and Evaluation are to:

- further develop the initial BM and BM scenarios based on D7.2
- provide an update on the Horizon Results Booster activities
- explore suitable revenue possibilities

- give insights into the BM testing approach
- present an updated GoTriple BM for end-users and institutions

Section 1 outlines general Business Model development reflections and gives an overview on the actual development status of the GoTriple platform. The entire BM design journey including a brief insight into the support activity by Horizon Results Booster (HRB)¹² service and a deep dive into the identification of additional revenue possibilities are described in Section 2. Section 3 provides an overview of the already conducted and planned BM testing activities. Finally, the report concludes with a summary and outlook (Section 4).

2 | BUSINESS MODEL DESIGN

The BM design process for GoTriple - a digital multi-stakeholder platform - is very challenging due to certain constraints such as i) restrictions concerning the function and feature set due to the specifications in the grant agreement, ii) uncertainty about whether the (multi-sided) platform offering is in line with stakeholder needs and iii) diverse interests of multi-disciplinary projects partners concerning the commitment to maintain the platform after the project ends.

The approach guided by WP7 aims to support the development of an economically sustainable BM after the project ends. For the design process, we used a mix of commonly known and widely used business analysis methods: competitor analysis, expert interviews, joint exploitation surveys and stakeholder analysis. The methods have been selected under the initial assumption that their complementary use will provide sufficient insights into the desirability, feasibility and viability of an early-stage BM. We collected data through expert interviews, online surveys, and secondary research. The interviews and compiled desk research results were analysed using qualitative content analysis and the online surveys were analysed descriptively. The four analysis methods provided valuable insights to inform the feasibility, desirability, and viability aspects of the early phase business model ideas of the GoTriple platform. Figure 3 shows the contribution of the different analysis methods concerning Cooper's¹³ interaction design principles, which are subsequently transformed into concrete inputs for each BMC building block of the platform BM.

¹² <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

¹³ Cooper, A., Reimann, R., & Cronin, D. (2007) *About face 3: the essentials of interaction design*. John Wiley & Sons.

FIGURE 3. CONTRIBUTION OF THE SELECTED BUSINESS ANALYSIS METHODS TO INFORM THE THREE BM SUCCESS FACTORS

2.1 Support from Horizon Results Booster (HRB) Service

To support the GoTriple BM and exploitation activities, the WP7 team, in accordance with the coordinator, decided to apply for Horizons Results Booster services. HRB is an initiative backed by the European Commission that aims to maximise the impact of research projects funded by FP7, Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>. Specifically, we applied and got accepted for the service Module C “Assisting projects to improve their existing exploitation strategy”. This service provided guidance and training to improve our existing project strategies towards effective exploitation and sustainable business of key exploitable results. We aimed to improve the following aspects:

- review of the key exploitable results of the project
- revise, complement and clarify existing BM designs and exploitation plans of project results
- techniques to identify all relevant stakeholders for a successful BM
- support to perform a risk analysis related to the exploitation of results.

In the course of this, we worked on the exploitation strategy including a sustainable BM of the GoTriple platform - the primary key exploitable result of the TRIPLE project. Together with project partners, we carried out two workshops where we worked on priorities, exploitation intentions, Business Model design (characterization of services), use options, and an exploitation roadmap. Based on templates provided by HRB, the WP7 team (KC, AU, DARIAH, CNRS, Net7 and OPERAS) provided the requested information, received feedback from HRB, revised the created

documents and discussed the gathered exploitation plans and BM designs within online workshops. In addition to our main KER, the GoTriple platform, we also worked on our second project KER, the multilingual vocabulary service. Our aim was to design this KER in such a way that it could be offered as a stand-alone service after the completion of the project. The WP7 team, supported by WP2 partners (KC, AU, DARIAH, CNRS, CNR, MWS, OAPEN, Net7, EGI, OPERAS), took part in two dedicated workshops to clearly identify the stakeholders, define the Unique Selling Point (USP) and bring the KER towards a sustainable business model. Based on our activities, provided information, workshop output, etc., we received a final report from HRB summarising the project dissemination and exploitation strategy concerning the two defined KERs.

Due to the successful collaboration with HRB and the good results achieved, the WP7 team decided to apply for a follow-up HRB service called “Business Plan Development”. This activity started in April 2022 and will support the TRIPLE project in the final steps of the Business Model development and the entire exploitation activities e.g. the creation of the exploitation roadmap.

2.2 Desirability

The starting point in terms of “Desirability” for the platform design and for the BM design is the “End-User”. Prior to developing customer profiles, interviews with customers were undertaken.¹⁴ The resulting eight end-user personas contained demographic information, a user story, a narrative, pain points and goals, as well as a rating of their technical proficiency, research participation, and collaborative experience. It may be inferred that the user-centric platform design was the focal point of the persona creation, which was based on early discoveries of user requirements. Since the number of users is a vital metric for the platform's acceptability and sustainability, institutional customers (Universities, Libraries, etc.) were excluded from the early stage of the business model development.

As part of the earlier phases of the stakeholder analysis activities, we created a stakeholder context diagram (see Figure 4) to give an overview of the main stakeholder groups of external as well as internal stakeholders.

¹⁴ Forbes, P.; De Paoli, S.; Błaszczynska, M.; Maryl, M. TRIPLE Deliverable: D3.1 Report on User Needs (Version Draft). Zenodo 2020.

FIGURE 4. STAKEHOLDER NETWORK ANALYSIS V1

For a more detailed analysis, we have reiterated the entire GoTriple stakeholder network (Figure 5). By doing so, we analysed the data, money and benefit flows, the actor roles, and which actors have customer needs. This network analysis gives us a deeper insight into the network and where flows may be missing. We definitely see a need for more incoming money flows to keep the platform running after the funding period. Our ideas regarding revenue opportunities for the platform are described in detail in chapter 2.3.

FIGURE 5. STAKEHOLDER NETWORK ANALYSIS V2

Furthermore, we conducted workshops with all of the innovative service partners to get a deeper understanding of the offered functions and features. In these workshops, we filled out data-driven business canvases to specify different components of the innovative services. See the filled-out canvas for the TRIPLE recommender system in the following:

FIGURE 6. DATA-DRIVEN BUSINESS CANVAS EXAMPLE FOR RECOMMENDER SERVICE

To align the GoTriple offerings with the user/customer needs, we used the Value Proposition Canvas by Osterwalder et al.¹⁵. Here, we identified the pains, gains, and jobs to be done for both customer groups (end-users, and institutional customers). After this, we tried to match the outcome with the offerings of the GoTriple platform. This matching process allows us to evaluate the alignment of the GoTriple offerings with the customer requirements. The filled-out canvas (see Figure 6) was then used to derive assumptions for the BM testing process described in Section 3.

¹⁵ Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y., Papadakos, P., Bernarda, G., Papadakos, T., & Smith, A. (2014). Value proposition design. John Wiley & Sons.

FIGURE 7. VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS FOR INSTITUTIONS

2.3 Viability

In the area of BM Viability, questions regarding the financial viability of GoTriple need to be answered. How is the platform's income made up, and who are the paying customers? Can the planned revenues (grants, membership fees, in-kind contributions, donations, etc.) cover the costs incurred?

Identifying Revenue Possibilities

Supported by the WP7 partners, we conducted an in-depth revenue analysis to identify promising revenue possibilities for GoTriple based on successful revenue models of other open science platforms. In Table 1, the content of the analysis is depicted.

TABLE 1. EXCERPT FROM IN-DEPTH REVENUE ANALYSIS

Name of Platform / URL	Typology	Organization Types	Finance Types
Academia / https://www.academia.edu/	science-oriented social media	for profit (enterprise)	premium subscriptions ads
Biblissima / http://beta.biblissima.fr	shadow library	non profit (organisation)	public funding
ScienceOpen / https://www.scienceopen.com/	dissemination platform	for profit (startup)	paid services
Unpaywall / https://unpaywall.org/	search engines and directories for OA resources	non profit (startup)	funding, membership, API
Google Scholar / https://scholar.google.com/	academic search engine	for profit (part of enterprise)	cross-financed
Mendeley / https://www.mendeley.com/	science-oriented social media	for profit (part of enterprise)	premium subscription, cross financed
Humanities Commons / https://hcommons.org/	science-oriented social media	non profit (organisation)	public funding, donations
HuNI (Humanities Networked Infrastructure) / https://huni.net.au/#/search	library catalogues and discovery systems	non profit (organisation)	public funding, partner contribution
isidore / https://isidore.science/	academic search engines	non profit (part of institution)	public & institutional funding
arXiv.org / https://arxiv.org/	search engines and directories for OA resources	non profit (part of institution)	member contributions, donations, in-Kind
JSTOR / https://www.jstor.org	search engines and directories for OA resources	non profit (part of institution)	subscriptions, fees
CORE / https://core.ac.uk/	search engines and directories for OA resources	non profit (part of institution)	paid services + In-Kind + institutional funding

Center for Open Science (COS) / https://cos.io/	dissemination platform	non profit (organisation)	sponsorship, donations, paid services
Nextstrain / https://nextstrain.org/	disciplinary academic database	non profit (startup)	donations
DataCite / https://datacite.org/	multidisciplinary academic databases	non profit (organisation)	membership fees
Zotero / https://www.zotero.org	science-oriented social media	non profit (project)	funding
Figshare.com / figshare.com	repositories - institutional or subject	non profit (part of enterprise)	cross-financed
OpenAIRE / https://explore.openaire.eu/	repositories - institutional or subject	non profit (organisation)	funding
Zenodo / www.zenodo.org	repositories - institutional or subject	non profit (governance part of institution, partner organisations providing additional funding)	Similar structure as arxiv.org, but without membership fees: Host organisation (CERN) and affiliated organisations providing baseline. Project funding for development.
DataSearch (Beta) / https://datasearch.elsevier.com/#/	academic search engines	for profit (part of enterprise)	cross-financed
IrisAI / https://iris.ai/	academic search engines	for profit (startup)	funding, premium accounts
Lens.org / https://www.lens.org/	academic search engines	for profit (enterprise)	funding, paid services (API)
ORCID / https://orcid.org/	multidisciplinary academic databases	non profit (organisation)	membership fee (basic/premium) - individual researchers will never pay, membership is for organisations and consortia
Researchgate / https://www.researchgate.net/	science-oriented social media	for profit (enterprise)	advertisement, burning (venture) capital, partnerships
Semantic Scholar / https://www.semanticscholar.org/	academic search engines	non profit (part of institution)	institutional & private funding

For each of these examples in Table 1, the following need to be provided by the analysis partner:

- **Please describe in detail possible revenue streams for the GoTriple platform (apart from funding or in-kind contribution)**, e.g. sponsoring, donations, partner contributions, membership fees, ads etc. What is the platform offering for X €? What is the benefit for the paying customer?
- **Recommendations for GoTriple:** which revenue possibilities are eligible/meaningful for GoTriple and why?
- **Additional information, e.g. images or screenshots of pricing models etc.**

Based on this information, we discussed (in various rounds) and selected suitable revenue possibilities for the GoTriple platform. The following possible revenue models for TRIPLE have been identified:

- Donations
- Sponsorship
- Memberships / Gold Services

In terms of designing business model scenarios for these revenue possibilities, we conducted two revenue model design workshops with consortium partners (KC, CNRS (Huma-Num), OAPEN, AU, MWS, Net7, MEOH).

Donations

In the workshops mentioned above with consortium partners (KC, CNRS (Huma-Num), OAPEN, AU, MWS, Net7, MEOH), we identified (micro-) donations as a suitable revenue possibility for GoTriple. Donations in any form are already utilised by Open Science platforms. Therefore, we reiterated the idea with the whole consortium and agreed that this is a simple, low-cost, low-maintenance way to generate small additional revenues for the platform and also allows the users of the platform to participate monetarily in the GoTriple mission. In the following, we conducted a Donation Solutions Analysis to identify the donation add-in services that we could integrate into the GoTriple platform. In this analysis, we identified different donation service providers and gathered information on the following characteristics:

- Fee
- Payment type
- Web format
- Specialised donation form (y/n)
- Option of recurring donations (y/n)
- Tax receipt (y/n)
- Donor database (y/n)
- Thank you mail (y/n)
- Campaign thermometer / goal meter (y/n)

Based on the characteristics, we ranked the donation service providers and identified DonorBox¹⁶ as the most suitable provider. Table 2 depicts the overview of the providers and characteristics.

Rank	Name	Fee	Note	Payment type	Web format	Specialized donation form	Support recurring donations	Tax receipt	Donor Database	Thank you email	Campaign thermometer/goal meter
1	DonorBox	4.4%+0.3/transaction for credit card (for EU cards is 2.9%+0.25) OR 2.3% for bank transfer = 1.5%donor box fee+(credit card stripe/paypal 2.9%+0.3 per transaction OR stripe ACH/Direct bank transfer 0.8%) ...2.2%+0.3 discount on stripe and paypal for nonprofits (check with stripe/paypal)from 2.9% to 1.4% for EU cards	More potent, customizable and cheaper	Stripe/paypal or bank transfer	Embedded form, pop up form or donor box campaign page	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y?
2	GiveWP	149/year (basic features)	Good alternative if donations are more than 3,000/year. Has a good free version for WP	Stripe and paypal		Y	Y	?	Y	Y?	Y
	Charitable	107/year (basic features)	WP donation plugin. GiveWP is better								
	Givinway	7%platform fee+stripe/paypal fee	Expensive, less features								
	Qgiv	3.95%+0.3 per transaction+1% AMEX	fundraising all-in-one platform (only US?)	AMEX (only US?)		Y	Y		Y		Y
	Donately	4%platform fee+(credit card stripe/paypal 2.9%+0.3 OR ACH/Direct bank transfer 0.8%)+stripe/paypal discount for nonprofit	Expensive, less features		Donation form and donation page (no embedd form)						
	iDonate	?	For large nonprofits, personalized service								
	Stripe	((1.4% EU cred cards OR 2.9%int cred card)+0.25 fix) OR 0.35 bank transfer ...discount for nonprofits	Missing donation features	Card, bank or others (Alipay, EPS, Klarna...)		N	Y?	N	N?	N?	N
	Paypal	((1.8% EU cred cards OR 3.8 %int cred card) + 0.35fix fee) OR 0.39 bank transfer.....1.7% fee+0.35 discount for nonprofits	Missing donation features			N	Y?	N	N?	N?	N
	Hivebrite	?	Community platform with donation option.								

TABLE 2. OVERVIEW ON DONATION SOLUTION ANALYSIS

Memberships / Gold Services and Sponsorships

In the workshops mentioned above with consortium partners (KC, CNRS (Huma-Num), OAPEN, AU, MWS, Net7, MEOH), we filled out structured revenue model canvases for the revenue models 1) donations, 2) sponsorship, and 3) membership/gold services to structure the design process and collect all important aspects of the revenue models. The revenue model canvas aims at specific target groups, propositions, benefits for target groups, and further task and implementation processes for each revenue opportunity. Following discussions in workshops and consortium meetings, we decided to focus on the revenue possibilities of donations and membership/gold services. The following outlines our actions regarding the specification of the chosen revenue possibilities.

¹⁶ <https://donorbox.org>

FIGURE 8: WORKSHOP WHITEBOARD FOR MEMBERSHIP & SPONSORSHIP FOR INSTITUTIONS

FIGURE 9. REVENUE MODEL CANVAS FOR MEMBERSHIP & SPONSORSHIP FOR INSTITUTIONS

As a preparational step towards implementing a revenue model that secures the viability and sustainability of the GoTriple platform, the identified data-driven features were used to draft three distinct membership bundles. Each bundle of a higher category included all features from the previous bundle. The first draft version, which included a “silver”, “gold”, and “platinum” membership, is shown in Figure 10.

FIGURE 10. INSTITUTIONAL MEMBERSHIP BUNDLES VERSION 1

As different project partners provide the GoTriple features, an internal assessment of the ability to provide each feature was initiated. In an exchange with the technical specialists of WP4 and WP5, it became evident that restricting access to some of the selected features to specific members would not have been possible. Accordingly, the first draft was reworked, and the decision was made to opt for two membership bundles instead. The draft for the final “sustaining” membership and “visionary” membership is depicted in Figure 11.

FIGURE 11. INSTITUTIONAL MEMBERSHIP BUNDLES VERSION 2

The main focus in designing the membership bundles was on proposing advanced visibility within the social science and humanities community, providing metadata access and granting a seat in the GoTriple Committee. Additional features were gradually added to the bundles throughout the ongoing evaluation efforts. Ideation efforts on these two membership bundles lead to two membership plans presented in Figure 12.

Visionary Membership

Logo on GoTriple Platform and Selected Materials: Be visible to the world as an innovative institution that is at the forefront of European SSH research

Discovery Platform API: Include GoTriple directly in your institution's own retrieval solution for easier

Sustainable Membership

Logo on GoTriple Platform and Selected Materials: Be visible to the world as an innovative institution that is at the forefront of European SSH research

Discovery Platform API: Include GoTriple directly in your institution's own retrieval solution for easier

FIGURE 12. MEMBERSHIP PLANS FOR THE GOTRIPLE PLATFORM

To evaluate our membership ideas, we conducted interviews with decision-makers in the SSH research field; the results of the interviews are described in chapter 3.2.

The next steps are to integrate the information on donations and memberships into the GoTriple platform. For that, we are designing and creating sub-pages on the platform for these two revenue streams (more information in chapter 4).

2.4 Feasibility

Feasibility refers to the general ability to carry out all connected technical and managerial activities as well as the business having access to all necessary key resources and key partners.

Here, we need to answer if the TRIPLE project has the necessary resources (personnel, know-how, infrastructure) and does the project have the right partners to implement the planned services.

The activities considering the technical feasibility were mainly performed by the technical / development Work Packages 2 (Data acquisition and categorisation), 4 (Integration and building of the TRIPLE platform) and 5 (Development and integration of innovative services). The outcome of implementation activities is the current release of GoTriple www.gotriple.eu.

To keep GoTriple technically sustainable after the project ends, we conducted a categorisation of GoTriple service components in terms of type (enabling, enhancing), short description, service provider and technology readiness level (TRL). Within this activity, we identified 18 service components, provided by 12 different service providers.

In order to ensure that each component will be provided beyond the life of the project, agreements are being established with each provider (supplier). The names of the agreements will depend on the type of supplier (i.e. Operational level agreements with internal suppliers, Underpinning Agreements or Contracts with external suppliers). This agreement structure, methodology and terminology follow the FitSM lightweight service management standard that is being used as the underlying framework.¹⁷

Another important aspect of the BM feasibility is the development of a reliable organisational body to ensure economic sustainability for GoTriple. Therefore, we developed an initial TRIPLE Governance framework that defines responsibilities and practices, policies, and procedures used to set strategic direction, achieve objectives, manage risks, and allocate resources. The current status of the TRIPLE Governance Model (see Figure 13) consists of the GoTriple Committee with 2 subgroups (User Engagement Subgroup and Data & Tool Subgroup), a Change Advisory Board (CAB) and includes the collaboration with OPERAS in its role as future operator of GoTriple. This collaboration is ensured by the involvement of a GoTriple representative in the OPERAS Service and Technology Board (STB).

The Partners' participation in the GoTriple Committee is voluntary, based on service to the community with not-for-profit purpose. However, it is expected that Partners are strongly committed to the purpose of the GoTriple Committee activities. The establishment, governance and operation of the GoTriple Committee are described in a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU). This MoU does not constitute a binding contract, nor does it create any financial obligation on either Partner towards the other Partner.

¹⁷ www.fitsm.eu

FIGURE 13. TRIPLE GOVERNANCE MODEL

The individual bodies (and roles) of the TRIPLE Governance Model are briefly described below.

GoTriple Committee

The people, entities and projects that allow the GoTriple Committee to work. This general assembly of the GoTriple Committee consists of the partners of the Data & Tool Subgroup (mainly service providers), the partners of the User Engagement Subgroup, the CAB and some internal experts.

Data & Tool Subgroup

- Direction and coordination of technical developments (innovations)
- Maintenance of services (updates,
- Ensure quality of data sources
- Expansion of data source

User Engagement Subgroup

- Collection and analysis of user feedback → suggestions for improvements or further developments
- Community management and user support
- Support of GoTriple communication channels
- IPR practices

OPERAS (AISBL)

- Legal and administrative coordination and support
- Dissemination, communication, marketing support

- Coordination of service management
- Community engagement
- Project funding scouting and coordination

Change Advisory Board (CAB)

- Maintain a list and descriptions of standard changes
- Evaluate non-standard changes, taking into account at least: benefits, risks, potential impact, technical feasibility, effort / cost, etc.
- Monitor the overall progress of change evaluation, approval, and implementation
- Review the change records in regular intervals, to identify trends or nonconformities or poor documentation / traceability

GoTriple Service and Technology Board (STP) Representative (in OPERAS STB Board)

- Advise OPERAS management on the priorities for evolving GoTriple
- Contribute to the OPERAS service strategy
- Communicate relevant developments regarding the service

3 | BUSINESS MODEL EVALUATION

In the process of designing a business model, assumptions must be formed about the model's major aspects, which serve as the basis for all expectations regarding the business model's future evolution after implementation. Therefore, it is necessary to rigorously analyse these assumptions with the aim to minimise uncertainty. When launching a new service such as the GoTriple platform, it is critical to assess and avoid potential market risks, primarily by evaluating the assumptions of the value proposition.

3.1 Assumption Mapping

Based on the actual value propositions for our main customer groups (researchers and institutions), all relevant assumptions were collected during a WP7 core team workshop. The assumptions were primarily deduced from the identified pains and gains in the respective value proposition canvas (see chapter 2.2, Figure 7). Furthermore, the workshop participants were also encouraged to reflect on any potential assumptions or risks that may influence the business model in any manner. After all the assumptions were collected, they were assessed based on the degree of importance and the level of evidence. The initial assumption map is displayed in Figure 14. This version of the assumptions has been presented and discussed in a larger WP7 setting where the participants were encouraged to give feedback and add further assumptions.

FIGURE 14. INITIAL ASSUMPTION MAP FOR INSTITUTIONS

The final version of the assumption map can be seen as a valuable guideline for further testing approaches, as it uncovers which assumptions were found to be the most critical for the business model.

3.2 Testing Methods

The next step after collecting relevant assumptions is to test the most important assumptions with appropriate experiments. Each experiment generates evidence and insights that allow us to learn and decide. Based on the evidence and the gained insights, we either adapt our GoTriple business model or continue testing if the evidence supports our direction.

The assumptions outlined in the upper right quadrant (very important, no evidence) for both customer groups (end users and institutions) have been grouped and analysed in terms of finding a suitable testing method. For structuring the testing activities, we created four testing cards, which outline the tested assumption (we believe that ...), the applied test method, the used

metrics, and the defined success criteria (we are right if ...). Two testing cards are presented in Figure 15.

FIGURE 15. BUSINESS MODEL TESTING CARDS

Within a WP7 workshop, we created two test cards for customer end-users (researchers) and two test cards for the customer group Institutions (Universities, Libraries, etc.). Below we outline in detail two test cards, one for each customer group.

Test card 1

Test name: SSH Institution Interviews

Assumption Examples: We believe that ...

- ... institutions want to anticipate trends in their field through access to Metadata
- ... SSH institutions/faculties are disappointed about the low perceived relevance of their work

- ... deans/library heads have a deceive influence on the purchasing decision for a GoTriple Membership bundle
- ... institutions have an interest in gaining visibility by putting their logo on GoTriple platform and GoTriople promotion material

Test method: To verify this, we will ...

- ... develop an initial interview guideline
- ... conduct two pilot interviews with SSH institutions
- ... refine interview guidelines and conduct further interviews

Metric: Level of agreement with key statements (1-5 Likert scale)

Criteria: 50% of measures are agreement or strong agreement

Testcard 2:

Test name: User test with lead users and early adopters

Assumption Examples: We believe that ...

- ... users consider the platform is easy to use
- ... users are satisfied with search results
- ... the visualisation are very useful to get an overview of a topic
- ... researchers value the recommendations from the platform

Test methods: To verify this, we will ...

- ... invite potential users to test the platforms
- ... conduct interviews with users and/or provide a feedback button on the platform which links to an online survey

Metric: satisfaction measurement with features (1-5 Likert scale), measurement of probability of recommending the platform (0 to 9 range)

Criteria: 50% or more of users rating 4 or 5 in general satisfaction, average of 5 concentering recommendation of the platform.

The test activities described in the test cards will be continued depending on the remaining WP7 resources and the results will be presented in the final Exploitation Report D7.4. At the time of the report, the following test activities had already been carried out or were in progress.

SSH Institution Interviews

Based on the previously described assumptions (Test card 1) the following main objectives for the interviews were defined:

- Determining the overall attractiveness of membership bundles to institutional customers in the social science and humanities context

- Obtaining first insights about the willingness to pay as well as approaching suitable pricing options
- Understanding institutional decision making in order to better be able to decisively target potential customers
- Evaluating the value perception of the suggested bundles and assessing the possibility of adding, removing or modifying parts of the bundles
- Identifying potential additional revenue models

These questions were transferred into an interview guideline and first test interviews have been scheduled to evaluate the guideline. The pilot interviews have been conducted with an SSH institution head of the University of Graz and a librarian (head of a faculty library at the University of Graz). The first insights can be summarised as follows. Despite the availability of a multitude of discovery platforms, the GoTriple platform was rated as very attractive due to e.g. the multilingual approach and the variety of useful functions and features (e.g. the discovery of web sources such as blog posts). The quality of the search results has been mentioned as the most important success factor of such platforms. The following functions and features were mentioned as desired or missing: profiles of researchers and students should be synched from other databases directly into GoTriple; missed indication if the search result is a book chapter, a conference proceeding, a journal proceeding, a blog entry etc.; a plus would be to know how the search result ranking is done, most of the platforms do not provide such information, this could be a potential USP.

The attractiveness of the membership bundles was evaluated differently. The main aim of the institute head was to attract more students. This seems to be hard to reach with the visualisation possibilities such as putting the institution logo on the platform and on selected promotion materials. The availability of meta-data was rated as attractive. On the subject of willingness to pay, both interview partners were cautious or undecided. This was due on the one hand to the difficulty of estimating the added value and on the other hand to the lack of not being in the position to decide on budgetary resources.

Based on the experience of the first two pilot interviews the interview guideline has been revised (see Appendix 1) and is now ready for further interviews.

Satisfaction Questionnaire

A satisfaction questionnaire was developed by WP3 on the Beta version of the GoTriple platform (see Figure 16). This questionnaire asks:

- Personal information (if the person is a e.g. a researcher)
- Where did the person hear of GoTriple
- How long the person uses GoTriple
- If a user account exists
- The perception of the platform (satisfaction, meeting the expectations, etc.)
- The navigation on the platform (e.g. easy to conduct a search)
- The confidence of e.g. recommending the platform

FIGURE 16. SCREENSHOT OF FEEDBACK BUTTON

During the next month, data will be gathered regarding user satisfaction via this feedback questionnaire.

3.3 Risk Assessment

An important part of the BM testing and evaluation task is to carry out a Risk Assessment. We have identified the risks of both KERs (the GoTRIPLE Platform and multilingual vocabulary service) and divided them into 4 clusters (Partnership-, Technological-, Market-, and IPR/Legal Risk Factors). After rating the importance and the probability of the risks, we developed potential mitigation interventions for both KERs (see Figure 17). Based on the risk grade and the success rate of the mitigation intervention, a conclusion is calculated that recommends graduated actions such as 1) action (red), 2) control (yellow) or 3) no action (green).

		HORIZON RESULTS BOOSTER		An initiative of the European Commission			
6.1.3 Risks Assessment and Priority Map							
	Key Exploitable Results	Importance of the risk (1 low- 10 high)	Probability of risk happening (1 low - 10 high)	Risk Grade	Scope and type of potential intervention	Feasibility/Successes of Intervention (1 low- 10 high)	Priority Level
Partnership Risk Factors							
1	Willingness of partners to join the future "organisation" to sustain GoTriple platform	7	3	21	Convincing partners during the project period	5	Between Control & No Action
2	(in-kind) contribution of partners too little to keep the platform up and running after project end	9	5	45	Getting commitment from partners during the project period	6	Control.
3	Poor collaboration btw. Digital Infrastructure provider like OPERAS, DARIAH, CLARIN, CESSDA is not working smoothly	5	3	15	Keeping DI partners constantly informed	7	Control.
Technological Risk Factors							
4	Performance of platform too slow	8	3	24	Constant monitoring and testing	7	Control.
5	Planned features are not working as specified	8	3	24	Constant monitoring and testing	6	Control.
6	Not enough update of the training database (search engine cannot work properly)	9	3	27	Constant monitoring and testing	7	Control.
7	Not enough update of the alignment of vocabularies (Thesaurus)	7	4	28	Constant monitoring and testing	5	Between Control & No Action
Market Risk Factors							
8	User base of platform too low (poor user acceptance)	10	5	50	Increase effort on communication and PR	6	Between Control & Action
9	Expected revenues via sponsoring/membership/donations are not realized as planned	6	8	48	Increase effort on communication and PR	5	Between Control & No Action

FIGURE 17. RISK ASSESSMENT AND PRIORITY MAP

Below a few examples of potential risks and their mitigation interventions are listed:

- Willingness of partners to join the future "organisation", the GoTriple Committee, to sustain GoTriple platform → convincing partners during the project period to join; be transparent in terms of benefits and expected contribution
- Planned GoTriple features and function are not working as specified → constant monitoring and testing
- User numbers do not develop as planned (growth too low) → increase effort on communication and PR base on the GoTriple user engagement strategy)

The initial risk assessment and priority map have been updated regularly and will be updated once more at the end of the project period.

3.4 Business Model Results

Based on the initial BM designs outlined in D7.1 and D7.2 we constantly further developed the GoTriple BM conducted by the WP7 project team and supported by the entire TRIPLE partners. The main focus was on improving the Value Proposition including the development of suitable Membership Bundles, getting more information on the targeted customer groups and getting a clear picture of the BM viability aspects in terms of potential revenue streams and cost estimations. In the following, the updated GoTriple BMs are divided into the 2 most important customer groups (Researchers, Institutions) in the form of a short description and presented by means of the Lean Canvas.

BM Customer Segment "Researcher"

Unique Value Proposition:

GoTRIPLE improves the access to open content and resources of social sciences and humanities (SSH) research and facilitates collaborations across disciplinary and language boundaries.

- Easy exploration of SSH research
- Find resources across language barriers
- Connect with SSH researchers to collaborate
- Fund your SSH research project

Targeted customer groups:

- SSH researchers (students, PhD students, junior and senior academics)
- Non-SSH researchers (businesses, NGO's, Policy Makers)
- Identified early adopters: Researchers from academic partners of TRIPLE consortium

Revenue Streams:

- Micro Donations from users (more details see chapter 2.3)
- In-kind contribution from TRIPLE consortium partners (organised in GoTriple Committee see chapter 2.4)
- OPERAS AISBL contribution for sustaining the core service components of GoTriple

FIGURE 18. GoTRIPLE BM FOR CUSTOMER SEGMENT RESEARCHER

BM Customer Segment “Institutions”

Unique Value Proposition:

GoTRIPLE improves the access to open content and resources of social sciences and humanities (SSH) research and facilitates collaborations across disciplinary and language boundaries.

- Make SSH research visible to the world (directing to the Sustaining Membership service bundle)
- Shape the future of exploring SSH research (directing to the Visionary Membership service bundle)

Targeted customer groups:

- SSH research focused institutions in Europe
 - EU focused Universities (about 280)
 - Private research centres (e.g. Max Plank Institute)
- Libraries
- Government-type institutions (e.g. statistical bureaus)

Revenue Streams:

- Membership Fees (Sustaining and Visionary Membership)
- Institutional one-time donations
- In-kind contribution from TRIPLE consortium partners (organised in GoTriple Committee see chapter 2.4)
- OPERAS AISBL contribution for sustaining the core service components of GoTriple

FIGURE 19. GoTRIPLE BM FOR CUSTOMER SEGMENT INSTITUTIONS

4 | CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Within the present report, we outlined the process and progress in terms of Business Model (BM) design and Business Model evaluation. We provided an overview of the TRIPLE Business Model development approach and a brief description of the current status of the GoTRIPLE Platform.

Additionally, we summarised our Horizon Results Booster activities and presented the entire BM design journey which includes a review of the used business analysis methods and insights into the crucial factors for developing a successful BM. In the field of “Desirability”, we illustrated our activities to match the customer requirements with the offered services of GoTRIPLE by using the Value Proposition Canvas. In terms of BM “Viability”, we described our activities in identifying possible revenue possibilities for GoTRIPLE, resulting in concepts for donation and membership solutions. In the area of BM “Feasibility”, we outlined the TRIPLE Governance Model (GoTRIPLE Committee) which should act as an organisational body to ensure economic sustainability for GoTRIPLE after the project ends.

Concerning BM testing we demonstrated the development and mapping of assumptions and the subsequent transformation into test procedures (test cards) including the definition of test methods, metrics and criteria. Hereafter, we provided the outcome of a Risk Assessment of the GoTriple Platform divided into four risk factors (Partnership-, Technological-, Market-, and IPR/Legal Risk Factors).

Finally, we presented the updated GoTriple Business Models divided into the two most important customer groups (Researchers, Institutions) in the form of a short description and presented by means of the Lean Canvas.

Outlook and next steps

Besides further testing activities outlined in chapter 3.2, we are currently focussing on the creation of mock-ups for sub-pages to present the donation possibilities and our membership offerings as well as the metrics dashboard to learn more about the GoTriple users.

Mock-ups for donation page and membership

We are currently working on mock-ups for the donation and membership pages on the GoTriple platform. Planned components for the **donation subpage** are:

- Content on GoTriples mission
- Main impacts of GoTriple
- Reasons for donating to GoTriple
- Explanations of what will be achieved with the donations
- Donation form (add-in by DonorBox)
- Get in touch form

Planned components for the **membership subpage** are:

- Content on GoTriples mission
- Benefits of becoming a member of GoTriple
- Logos of recent GoTriple members
- Motivations of recent GoTriple members
- Membership plans for “visionary” and “sustainable” memberships (what will be offered)
- Get in touch form

Metrics Dashboard

In collaboration with WP1 and WP3 we are currently creating a dashboard that will serve as an internal oversight of different metrics of the platform. This will enable us to monitor parameters such as user numbers, users' countries of origin, users' professional groups, and to plan explicit actions (e.g. marketing actions), for example, to draw the attention of underrepresented groups to the platform.

The current status of the developments on the subpages and the metrics dashboard will be reported in D7.4, the final report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy.

ANNEX

ANNEX 1: INTERVIEW GUIDELINE FOR INSTITUTIONS

This guideline proposes a rough direction how an interview with a decision maker of a potential early adopter institution can take place. The Interview is designed for 30 to 45 minutes.

It is important to recognize that these interviews are not sales pitches. While getting new leads is a benefit, the main goal is to understand the value perception of the GoTriple platform, gain insights about institutional decision-making and gatekeeping as well as generating innovative insights for other potential sources of monetization.

1. Clarifying the role of the interview partner (Getting to know each other)
 - Set the frame for the interview – it is not purely about making a sales pitch, but rather about evaluating the perceived benefit of a new academic platform.*
 - a. What is your role in their organization?
 - b. Do you have experience with discovery platforms? What kind (personal use, contract negotiations, decision making)?
 - c. Which ones does your institution use? Which do you license?
2. Understanding institutional decision-making
 - a. How much do you spend on digital platform licenses/memberships in general?
 - b. Who scouts possible new platform licenses/memberships? Who decides to buy licenses/membership fees?
3. Evaluating pains and gains
 - a. How do you perceive the visibility of SSH research in general? (follow-up!)
 - b. In which way can networking with driving SSH institutions boost the visibility of your department's work?
 - c. Are there any collaborations with (SSH) institutions or platforms already? Why/ why not? What is the benefit for you? (follow-up: Are you/your institution participating in any governance board)

- d. Do you struggle to find partner institutions and researchers for projects? What are the exact obstacles in this regard? Do you struggle with research funding? Would you consider crowdfunding as an option?
- e. How do you perceive the digital literacy of SSH researchers? (follow-up!)
- f. Is anticipating research trends interesting to you? What do you think about the usefulness of metadata?
- g. Would you be interested in advertising your organization by placing the logo prominently on an (SSH) discovery platform? If so, what do you hope to gain from it?
- h. Would you consider an in-kind contribution?

4. Showing what GoTriple can offer – our Unique Value Proposition

Present our Value Proposition in an appealing manner: We offer the platform for SSH research and give access to a network of institutions that want to be driving forces in their research field.

Try to emphasize the potential direct benefit for the customer. The unique services for end users also offer a good starting point.

You can use [this brochure](#) and [this visualization](#) for presentation purposes

5. Presenting the membership bundles

As of July 2022, the proposed membership options include the following:

Sustaining Membership	Visionary Membership
Logo on platform	Seat in governance board
Logo in selected materials	Meta Data Access
Discovery Platform API	Consortium Expertise Access
(Community Events)	
(Training Sessions)	

- a. What is particularly interesting?
 - b. Would you wish for any additional features in these memberships?
 - c. What is not interesting?
 - d. How would you rate these membership options in comparison to other platforms your organization currently has in use?
 - e. What do you think is a reasonable price for a GoTriple membership?
 - f. Would you be interested?
6. Open the floor for discussion and feedback
What else could be interesting about this platform? Can you imagine different use cases?
7. If the interview has the potential of turning into a lead, clarify communication channels for further inquiries.

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